

INTERRELATIONSHIPS OF COOKING KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND SKILLS OF G12 SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Cooking is an essential life skill that should be integral to every student's education. This study explored the interconnectedness of cooking knowledge, attitudes, and skills among Grade 12 senior high school students, focusing on cereal, starch, vegetable, and seafood dishes. Specifically, it examined how students' knowledge and attitudes toward cooking influenced their cooking skills. The study utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational design and partial enumeration population sampling to assess 80 male and female Grade 12 Cookery students aged 18 to 20 years old in the Division of Bukidnon during the School Year 2023-2024. Descriptive statistics, Pearson Correlation, and regression analysis were employed to analyze the data. The findings revealed that students generally had a good understanding of fundamental cooking concepts, indicating strong cooking knowledge. Additionally, students displayed a highly favorable attitude towards cooking, reflecting their enthusiasm and positive disposition toward cooking-related activities. Their cooking skills were also rated very satisfactory, demonstrating consistent performance. A significant positive relationship was found between students' cooking knowledge and their attitudes towards cooking. The regression analysis further revealed that cooking knowledge significantly influenced cooking skills, while attitudes played a supplementary role. However, attitudes did not directly influence skill improvement, suggesting the need for further research on a broader scale to validate these findings. The study concluded that while cooking knowledge is a key factor in skill development, attitudes enhance the application of this knowledge without directly predicting skill proficiency.

Keywords: *cooking knowledge, cooking attitudes, and cooking skills*

INTRODUCTION

The development of transversal competencies has been incorporated into the curricula of vocational education and training programs, such as the cooking program, as a means of enhancing employability. Students' success in cooking is largely dependent on their knowledge, attitudes, and abilities. One of the main components of lifelong learning systems is vocational education and training (VET), which tries to give people the interpersonal skills they will need in society as well as the technical knowledge, competence, and attitude needed to succeed in the workforce. It is the instrument to open doors to better jobs and more employability. Research on the subject has been conducted far more frequently in recent years, with an emphasis on its applicability and the variety of methods and elements that go into learning, particularly the connection between students' knowledge, attitudes, and abilities (Lopez & Lopez 2020).

The ability to carry out tasks linked to food preparation, which include washing, peeling, and chopping before cooking, has been referred to as cooking skills (Caraher et al., 2018). Scholars have noted that the development of personal cooking skills is contingent upon the possession of fundamental cooking knowledge and attitude (Larson et al., 2018). Additionally, the rise in scientific interest in this topic appears related to the global environment that supports the adoption of vocational education, such as cooking. Research indicates that enhanced culinary proficiency, encompassing attitudes and self-assurance in food preparation or the frequency of home meal preparation, could encourage nutritious eating practices, particularly concerning the uptake of fruits and vegetables. According to scientific research on enhanced cooking skills, one of the things that harms these practices is a person's ability to cook (Doe & Smith, 2021). The decline in passing down cooking knowledge to future generations and in schools has resulted in a notable decrease in cooking skills and positive attitudes toward cooking, negatively impacting an individual's ability to cook (Thompson & Harris, 2022).

Determining the relationships between G12 senior high school students' cooking knowledge, attitude, and skills is, therefore, essential to the Senior High School TVL Track's goal of effectively delivering the vocational education curriculum. Planning and managing the distribution of facilities and equipment required for the Commercial Cookery Technical-Vocational program can benefit from this endeavor.

A recent practical demonstration in a school's Cookery class noted that a significant number of G12 students demonstrated varying levels of cooking skills. While some students showcased excellent cooking skills and a positive attitude towards the task, others struggled with basic cooking techniques and lacked confidence (Sahd, 2019). Informal discussions with the students revealed that those with better cooking skills often had more exposure to cooking at home and a more positive attitude toward learning new recipes. On the other hand, students with limited cooking knowledge and skills often expressed a disinterest or negative attitude towards cooking, citing it as a chore rather than a valuable life skill (Lavelle et al., 2019). This observation highlights the need for a comprehensive study to explore the interrelationships between cooking knowledge, attitude, and abilities among G12 senior high school students. Understanding these

interrelationships can inform the development of targeted educational programs that enhance cooking skills and foster positive attitudes toward cooking.

The relationship between cooking knowledge, skills, and attitudes is not well documented in the Philippines, despite a wealth of research on the application of vocational education and training. Pascual et al. (2019) and Hinalinan et al. (2023) supported the claim that documentation on cooking knowledge, skills, and attitudes in the Philippines was lacking. Also, as to their relationship, there were only a few studies that established the relationship between cooking knowledge, cooking attitudes, and cooking skills (Putri et al., 2021). The researcher is aware of very few published local studies in this area concerning the subject matter.

In light of the dearth of research regarding the correlation between cooking knowledge, attitude, and skills in the community, this study ascertained the levels of cooking knowledge, attitudes, and skills among Grade 12 Senior High School students. School administrators would benefit from the study since it will give them pertinent data to assess how students' knowledge, attitudes, and abilities relate to those of students enrolled in Cookery NCII. The results would be put to use to improve, maintain, or extend the TVL Track's capacity to deliver top-notch instruction.

Framework

The study assumes that cooking knowledge and attitudes influence students' cooking skills, based on Nonaka's Transfer of Knowledge Theory (1994), which posited that knowledge significantly impacts learning outcomes and that attitude is a crucial factor in this relationship. The theory emphasized that the transfer of knowledge is essential to the learning process and is influenced by various factors, including attitude, aligning with the study's assumption that both knowledge and attitude shape cooking skills. In knowledge management, knowledge is created by transforming data into information and then into usable knowledge, a process necessary for developing unique skills (Dalkir & Beaulieu, 2017). Knowledge conversion theory further explains how knowledge is formed and interacts with attitudes to affect the skills acquired, highlighting the interaction between implicit and explicit knowledge, influenced by attitudes, the learning process, and the environment (Nonaka et al., 2001; Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995; Nonaka, 1994). Higher education contributes significantly by equipping students with essential tools to become effective knowledge workers, including fostering the right mindset, providing a supportive learning environment, offering guidance, and presenting teaching opportunities (Smith & Brown, 2020).

The study focused on examining how students' cooking knowledge and attitudes—two independent variables—affected their cooking skills, the dependent variable. A comprehensive review was conducted to define and contextualize cooking skills, considering both basic and systematic definitions and exploring their evolution through historical and contemporary contexts of food preparation (Jomori et al., 2018).

Cooking skills are influenced by various individual factors, particularly personal cooking knowledge (Farmer et al., 2021). This foundational knowledge is crucial for

developing effective culinary skills, impacting one's ability to perform diverse cooking tasks (Lavelle et al., 2019). Essential elements of cooking knowledge include understanding techniques, ingredient handling, and food safety practices (Sullivan, 2019). Without a solid grasp of these areas, mastering practical cooking skills is challenging. Well-informed individuals are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward cooking practices, as knowledge significantly shapes attitudes (Farmer & Cotter, 2021; Putri et al., 2021). A comprehensive understanding of cooking principles enhances skills and confidence in the kitchen, such as preventing foodborne illnesses through proper food safety practices. This competence positively influences attitudes toward cooking (Putri et al., 2021).

Ding and Zhang (2020) noted that attitudes toward cooking—shaped by perceptions, motivations, and feelings about food preparation—could influence cooking skills. Positive attitudes, characterized by enthusiasm and confidence, often stemmed from a solid knowledge base and were critical for skill development. Brown (2019) demonstrated that a positive attitude toward cooking significantly enhanced cooking skills, as increased confidence and enthusiasm led to more frequent practice and improved techniques, resulting in greater overall proficiency in the kitchen.

Practical cooking skills, such as proper knife handling, efficient time management, and effective use of tools, were significantly influenced by both knowledge and attitude (Sullivan, 2019). A positive attitude toward cooking could encourage more practice and skill refinement, while a solid understanding of cooking techniques enhances the execution of these skills (Farmer et al., 2021). Individuals who viewed cooking as a rewarding activity were more likely to practice and improve their skills compared to those who saw it as a chore (Putri et al., 2021). As proficiency increased, individuals often developed greater curiosity and a desire to learn new techniques, further enhancing their skills (Brown, 2019). A positive attitude not only motivates individuals to acquire and apply cooking knowledge but also improves their confidence and reduces anxiety related to cooking tasks, while gaining new knowledge could, in turn, boost one's attitude (Ding & Zhang, 2020).

The study emphasized the pivotal role of attitude in cooking, particularly how students' eagerness to learn cooking skills influences their competence. Attitudes toward cooking can either hinder or drive the development of cooking abilities, with willingness, defined as inclination or readiness, being essential for engaging in cookery activities. Research by Czap (2020) highlighted a significant relationship between cooking proficiency and attitudes, while Jomori et al. (2018) found that practical instruction and skill demonstration notably enhanced both cooking knowledge and attitudes. Challenges such as curriculum limitations and students' lack of prior food-related knowledge underscore the need for comprehensive food education (Burton et al., 2018). As cooking self-efficacy increased, so did cooking frequency, with a notable rise linked to a positive cooking attitude (Oleschuk et al., 2023). Furthermore, attitudes toward cooking in single-person households significantly impacted cooking frequency, nutritional choices, and overall diet quality, suggesting that societal initiatives like cooking classes or communal kitchens could be beneficial (Yong et al., 2019). However, negative attitudes and the limited effectiveness of current cooking education interventions highlight the need for

further research and more nuanced strategies to foster positive cooking behaviors (Sogari et al., 2018; Bruno, 2019). Cooking skills encompass not only personal knowledge but also confidence, attitude, and the execution of tasks like menu planning, grocery shopping, and preparing foods through various methods (Jomori et al., 2018; Doe, 2023).

The study emphasized the use of tools and equipment, adherence to procedures, safety habits, task completeness, and time management in cooking. According to Griffin (2018), kitchen utensils are crucial for tasks such as cutting, cooking, and baking, and their effective use simplifies and improves efficiency in the kitchen. Similarly, incorporating tools and equipment into cooking training is vital for developing students' skills, as these tools facilitate learning and boost confidence (Aishah et al., 2019; da Costa Pelonha et al., 2023). Proper equipment ensured efficient task completion, whereas inadequate tools led to inefficiency and negatively impacted students' performance (Woods, 2018; Hernandez, 2019; Panganiban, 2020). Kondylakis et al. (2022) noted that modifying common recipes could enhance cooking variety, while Nakabe et al. (2021) demonstrated that optimizing cooking procedures could reduce cooking time. Safety work habits, which involve effective hygiene practices and safety training, are essential for reducing risks and preventing accidents in cooking (Mohammed et al., 2017; Yared & Abdulrazak, 2015). Comprehensive safety measures, including the use of protective equipment and maintaining cleanliness, are essential for preventing contamination and accidents (Ismael, 2018; Chellaiyan et al., 2018). Additionally, task completion principles, emphasizing planning and anticipation of obstacles, are key to efficiency and success in cooking (Bondalapati, 2022; Collentine, 2019), and practical learning methods significantly enhanced student mastery and engagement (Erdiana, 2019; Badariah, 2022). Effective time management in cooking is significant for optimizing efficiency, ensuring timely meal preparation, and reducing stress, which enhances cookery outcomes (Smith, 2024). For cookery students, mastering this skill is crucial as it affects their learning outcomes and practical abilities, with techniques like batch cooking, using time-saving appliances, and multitasking significantly improving efficiency (Doe, 2024; Adams & Brown, 2018; Johnson, 2021). Utilizing timers, alarms, and checklists helped manage cooking times and prevent overcooking (White & Green, 2021), while pre-demonstration planning and mise en place further reduced cooking time (Smith, 2022; Wilson & Green, 2020). However, challenges such as unexpected delays and multitasking difficulties arose, necessitating flexible scheduling and prioritization to address effectively (Clark, 2022).

The study emphasized the role of hands-on cooking classes in cultivating a synergistic relationship between cooking knowledge, attitudes, and skills, which significantly enhanced culinary competence and enjoyment. By applying the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Marklinder et al., 2022), the research highlighted how individuals' cooking behaviors were shaped by their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. TPB suggested that cooking behaviors were influenced by one's knowledge, attitudes, and skills regarding food preparation and safety (Marmot et al., 2022; Marklinder et al., 2022; Herman et al., 2023). The findings revealed a complex interplay between these factors, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to improve cooking skills (Marklinder et al., 2022; Mengi Çelik et al., 2023). The cyclical relationship between cooking knowledge, attitude, and skills was mutually reinforcing:

knowledge underpinned skill development, positive attitudes enhanced skill acquisition, and developed skills stimulated further learning. Addressing all three aspects was crucial for advancing students' overall cooking abilities (Farmer & Cotter, 2021).

The interplay of these variables is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of the Study

Research Questions

The study intended to determine the interrelationship between knowledge, attitudes, and cooking skills of Grade 12 students.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of students' knowledge in cooking?
2. What is the level of students' attitude toward cooking?
3. What is the level of students' cooking skills in terms of:
 - 3.1 use of tools and equipment;
 - 3.2 application of procedures;
 - 3.3 safety work habits;
 - 3.4 completeness of tasks; and
 - 3.5 time management?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the students' cooking knowledge and their attitude toward cooking?
5. Do the students' knowledge and attitude significantly influence their cooking skills?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative descriptive correlational research approach utilizing partial enumeration population sampling. The research participants in this study involved 80 Grade 12 Cookery Students, aged between 18 years old up to 20 years old, in the Division of Bukidnon for School Year 2023-2024. The study was conducted on-site. The following statistical tools were utilized in the study. For problems 1, 2, and 3, descriptive statistics like mean, frequency, and standard deviation were employed. For problem 4, Pearson Correlation was used to determine the strength and direction of the relationship. Regression analysis was also performed to explore the predictive power of knowledge and attitude on cooking skills.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the level of students' knowledge in cooking?

The study's results highlighted a generally strong level of cooking knowledge among students, with 31.25% demonstrating very good knowledge and 6.25% achieving outstanding ratings as shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Students' Knowledge in Cooking

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
9 – 10	Outstanding	5	6.25
7 – 8	Very Good	25	31.25
5 – 6	Good	30	37.50
3 – 4	Fair	17	21.25
1 – 2	Poor	3	3.75
	Total	80	100.0
	Overall Mean		5.81
	Interpretation		Good
	SD		1.91

However, 21.25% of students had only fair knowledge, and 3.75% showed poor knowledge, indicating notable gaps that required additional educational support. Tailored instruction for slower learners and fostering greater engagement and enthusiasm in cooking were essential for improving proficiency. The challenge of knowledge retention was evident, as some students struggled to remember lessons despite previous discussions with their cookery teacher (Alsarayreh, 2022). To address these retention issues, empirical evidence suggested that integrating technology, such as educational videos, could enhance learning by providing visual and auditory stimuli, fostering group learning, and creating engaging and effective educational experiences (Huang et al., 2019; Iyer, 2020; Cabrerros, 2023).

Research Question 2. What is the level of students' attitude toward cooking?

Table 2 illustrated that students generally held a highly favorable attitude toward cooking, with an average mean score of 4.06 and a standard deviation of 0.35, indicating a consistent and positive response among participants. Specifically, 85.0% of students demonstrated a highly favorable attitude, and 8.75% showed an exceptionally positive outlook, while only 6.25% were categorized as having a moderate attitude, with no students falling into the low or very low categories. This overall positive outlook reflected students' strong inclination toward viewing themselves as proficient cooks and their eagerness to explore new culinary skills (Hollywood et al., 2018).

Table 2
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Students' Attitude in Cooking

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	7	8.75
3.51-4.50	High	68	85.0
2.51-3.50	Moderate	5	6.25
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.0
Total		80	100.0
Overall Mean			4.06
Interpretation			High
SD			0.35

Specific Indicators of Students' Attitude to Cooking	M	Interpretation	SD
1 It is important to know how to prepare food.	4.40	High	0.63
2 I enjoy cooking and cooking is fun.	4.20	High	0.66
3 Making meals at home helps me to eat more healthfully.	4.18	High	0.69
4 I believe that having the ability to prepare food is considered important.	4.16	High	0.58
5 I appreciate the sense of accomplishment that comes from mastering new cooking skills	4.16	High	0.51
6 I am happy and confident every time I cook.	4.14	High	0.63
7 I do NOT like to cook because it takes too much time. *	4.13	Low*	0.54
8 I have a genuine love for food and cooking as a means of nourishing myself and others.	4.11	High	0.64
9 I approach cooking tasks with a positive and open-minded attitude	4.10	High	0.63
10 I like cooking because this is my hobby.	4.10	High	0.70
11 I demonstrate enthusiasm for experimenting with different ingredients and cooking techniques.	4.08	High	0.59
12 Cooking is interesting and I actively seek out new recipes and cuisines to try.	4.04	High	0.60

13	I take pride in the presentation and taste of dishes I have prepared.	4.03	High	0.71
14	I can manage time effectively to ensure meals are prepared and served on schedule.	3.99	High	0.63
15	Cooking is my stress reliever.	3.98	High	0.83
16	I can show self-assurance while handling kitchen tools and equipment.	3.95	High	0.59
17	Preparing meals at home would NOT improve the health of my diet. *	3.91	Low*	0.64
18	I find that preparing meals is a worthwhile use of my time.	3.89	High	0.69
19	It is easy to prepare meals and I exhibit comfort and ease when following recipes and cooking procedures	3.88	High	0.75
20	I display a willingness to take on cooking challenges and problem-solve independently.	3.84	High	0.74

**reversely scored*

Legend for reversely scored items: 4.51-5.00 (Very Low); 3.51-4.50 (Low);

2.51-3.50 (Moderate)

1.51-2.50 (High);

1.00-1.50 (Very High)

Most indicators fell within the "High" category, showcasing strong positive attitudes toward cooking, including its importance, enjoyment, health benefits, accomplishment, confidence, and willingness to experiment. The highest mean indicator, "It is important to know how to prepare food" (Mean: 4.40), underscored students' recognition of the value of cooking skills for self-sufficiency and creating nutritious meals, aligning with Alsarayreh (2022). The second highest mean indicator, "I enjoy cooking and cooking is fun" (Mean: 4.20), emphasized how enjoyment and fun in cooking fostered engagement and willingness to try new recipes, supporting greater retention of cooking skills (Anderson and Lee, 2020). The third indicator, "Making meals at home helps me to eat more healthfully" (Mean: 4.18), highlighted the perceived health benefits of home-cooked meals, motivating students to practice cooking and enhance their skills (Wright and Rowell, 2020). However, reverse-coded indicators, such as "I do NOT like to cook because it takes too much time" (Mean: 4.13) and "Preparing meals at home would NOT improve the health of my diet" (Mean: 3.91), fell into the "Low" category. These responses reflected students' busy schedules and perceived time constraints, which hindered their culinary skill development and contributed to negative attitudes toward cooking (Brown and Davis, 2022; McGowan et al., 2019).

Additionally, limited cooking skills and insufficient nutritional education affected students' perceptions of the health benefits of home-cooked meals (da Costa Pelonha et al., 2023; Coe et al., 2023; Gondin et al., 2022). To address these issues, interventions were needed to challenge misconceptions about healthy cooking and educate students on efficient, affordable meal preparation (Puri and Jaiswal, 2023). Integrating high school cooking courses into curricula could also improve food literacy and promote healthier eating habits (LeBlanc et al., 2022).

Research Question 3. What is the level of students' cooking skills in terms of:

- 3.1 Use of Tools and Equipment;
- 3.2 Application of Procedures;
- 3.3 Safety Work Habits;
- 3.4 Completeness of Tasks; and
- 3.5 Time Management?

Table 3 provides a summary of students' cooking skills, highlighting mean scores, interpretations, and standard deviations across various dimensions. The highest-rated dimension was the use of tools and equipment, with a mean score of 3.38, reflecting very satisfactory performance. This high rating resulted from participants effectively using and applying tools and equipment for various cooking tasks, including cutting, chopping, measuring, mixing, and utilizing appliances like blenders and grinders. Students' familiarity with these tools, bolstered by prior knowledge from exploratory subjects on kitchen equipment, contributed to their confidence and competence in this area. Their ample opportunities for hands-on practice in both classroom and home settings, along with training on proper use and maintenance, enhanced their skills and performance. Conversely, the lowest mean score, though still very satisfactory, was 2.62 for Safety Work Habits. This lower rating resulted from less emphasis on safety during skills demonstrations, leading to inconsistent adherence to safety precautions.

Table 3

Summary Table of Students' Cooking Skills

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Use of Tools and Equipment	3.38	Very Satisfactory	0.45
Application of Procedures	3.06	Very Satisfactory	0.33
Time Management	2.85	Very Satisfactory	0.35
Completeness of Tasks	2.78	Very Satisfactory	0.46
Safety Work Habits	2.62	Very Satisfactory	0.41
Overall	2.94	Very Satisfactory	0.38

The complexity of safety protocols, including the use of personal protective equipment and the proper handling of sharp objects, likely contributed to students' lesser focus on these habits, potentially resulting in complacency and reduced diligence.

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between the students' cooking knowledge and their attitude toward cooking?

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between students' cooking knowledge and their attitudes towards cooking.

Table 4

Result of the Test of Relationship between the Students' Cooking Knowledge and their Attitude in Cooking

	Measures	Cooking Knowledge
Attitude Towards Cooking	Pearson Correlation	.243*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.030

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The Pearson Correlation coefficient of 0.243 between students' cooking knowledge and their attitudes toward cooking, with a significance level of 0.030, indicated a positive relationship and led to the rejection of the null hypothesis (Ho₁). This suggested that as students' cooking knowledge increased, their attitudes toward cooking also improved. Observations revealed that greater knowledge fostered a more positive attitude toward recipes and techniques, making cooking less intimidating and more enjoyable. Hartmann et al. (2018) found that increased cooking knowledge led to more frequent meal preparation and a more favorable attitude toward cooking. A deeper understanding of cooking processes enhanced students' appreciation for cooking as both an art and a valuable skill, further improving their attitudes (Farmer et al., 2021). Awareness of the nutritional benefits of cooking also encouraged healthier eating habits and a greater commitment to cooking. As students' cooking knowledge advanced, they achieved better outcomes in performance tasks, which in turn enhanced their enjoyment and positive attitude toward cooking, creating a cycle of continual engagement (Lavelle et al., 2019). This ongoing motivation to develop culinary skills was driven by both increased knowledge and a positive attitude, leading to further skill enhancement (Mötteli et al., 2022). Nonaka's Transfer of Knowledge Theory supported this by emphasizing that knowledge transfer, influenced by attitudes, was crucial for skill development. The theory highlighted how knowledge and attitudes interacted to shape cooking skills, validating the study's assumption of their importance in skill acquisition.

Research Question 5. Do the students' knowledge and attitude significantly influence their cooking skills?

Ho₂: Students' cooking knowledge and attitude do not significantly influence their cooking skills.

Table 5 shows the regression analysis of how students' cooking knowledge and attitudes influence their cooking skills.

Table 5

Regression Analysis of the Influence of Students' Cooking Knowledge and Attitude on their Cooking Skills

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.90	.136		14.02	.000
Cooking Knowledge	.191	.006	.966	30.01**	.000
Attitude towards Cooking	-.018	.034	-.017	-.536	.593

Model Summary				
R = .962	R ² = .925	Adjusted R ² = .923	F = 474.50**	p = .000

The model's significance (F = 474.50, p = .000) indicated that cooking knowledge and attitudes collectively explained a substantial portion of the variability in students' cooking skills, with 92.5% of the variance accounted for (R² = .925). The low p-value strongly rejected the null hypothesis. This implied that as students' cooking knowledge increased, their practical skills also improved, supported by foundational research emphasizing the importance of knowledge in skill development (Jomori et al., 2018). Although both knowledge and attitude were considered, only cooking knowledge showed a significant impact on skill improvement, with each unit increase in knowledge corresponding to a 0.191 increase in skills (B = 0.191, t = 30.01, p = .000). This underscored the role of technical expertise in skill acquisition, as opposed to attitude, which did not significantly predict skill development on its own. Knowledge provided the essential information and techniques necessary for effective cooking, while a positive attitude, though important for engagement and enjoyment, did not directly influence skills without sufficient knowledge. This finding aligned with research highlighting the critical role of practical knowledge (Thompson et al., 2019; Garcia et al., 2020) and suggested that while attitudes might enhance the application of knowledge, they were less critical in isolation. The study also pointed to other potential factors influencing cooking skills, such

as prior experience, learning environment, and personal attributes, which warranted further exploration for a comprehensive understanding of skill development.

Conclusions

The study successfully achieved its objective by thoroughly investigating and assessing various aspects related to cooking among G12 Senior High School cookery students in the Division of Bukidnon. Based on the findings, students demonstrated a generally positive understanding of cooking coupled with a highly favorable attitude toward cooking. The Transfer of Knowledge Theory helps explain the positive disposition by highlighting the role of attitude in acquiring knowledge and developing skills. Although cooking knowledge significantly impacts cooking skills, attitudes toward cooking did not show a significant predictive relationship with skills in this study. The theory demonstrates how knowledge and attitudes interact, supporting the finding that cooking knowledge directly improves skills, while attitudes play a supplementary role in applying knowledge. This suggests that while attitudes are important for interest and enjoyment, they do not directly lead to skill improvement without a strong foundation of knowledge and practical experience. The study emphasizes the need for a solid theoretical understanding and technical expertise in cooking, noting that while cooking knowledge was measured through objective assessments, attitudes were more subjective and may influence skill development indirectly by enhancing the application of knowledge.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are formulated:

1. TVL-HE teachers may implement targeted educational interventions, such as extra practice sessions, personalized coaching, and additional resources like Cooking Apps, YouTube channels, cookery books, cookery clubs, and workshops, to address gaps in cooking knowledge among students with fair to poor knowledge, while maintaining a positive learning environment that fosters enthusiasm and engagement, enhancing knowledge retention through technology like videos and interactive platforms, and continuing to incorporate rigorous safety practices into skills demonstrations with additional training focused on safety procedures.
2. School Heads/Curriculum Planners: continue integrating more practical cooking sessions or workshops to strengthen students' cooking skills and encourage teachers to include time management training in the curriculum to help students excel in this area.
3. Parents: continue to support and encourage their children's interest in cooking by offering opportunities to practice at home and explore various local recipes.
4. Future researchers should conduct further investigations into factors influencing cooking skills among students, such as socio-economic background, cultural influences, and personal motivations; explore innovative teaching methodologies and interventions for more effective skill development; examine additional elements like prior cooking experience, learning environments, and personal attributes; and

evaluate assessment tools to ensure their comprehensibility, reliability, and variety of test items.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher adhered to certain ethical protocols and procedures in the conduct of the study. The researcher was guided by the ethical principles of respect for persons, justice, and beneficence as outlined in the Belmont report (1978). First, the researcher sought formal approval from the administrator of the institution to conduct the study and informed their respective students of their inclusion as participants in the study. The informed consent process involved providing participants with a consent form. Only those who provided their approval to participate were included, while those who declined or did not give consent were excluded from the study. It was emphasized that students had the option not to join as participation is voluntary, and they could withdraw from the study at any time if they felt the need to do so. The instrument served as the primary source of data and was disseminated to the intended participants upon approval of the request by the respective authorities of the institution, the school's Research Ethics Committee, and written consent from the participants.

Second, the researcher oriented the participants on the nature, and process of the survey including the risk that they may share their personal or confidential information, or they may experience discomfort while completing the questionnaire or performance task. The comfort and safety during the activity were the top priorities. The researcher and subject teacher collaborated closely to assess and mitigate potential risks associated with the practical cooking demonstration of the students. Together, they established clear safety protocols and provided thorough reminders to students on safe cooking practices and emergency procedures. All data collected during this study were kept confidential and private. The participants' identities remained anonymous in any reports or publications. Only authorized research personnel had access to the data, ensuring strict confidentiality measures were maintained throughout the study.

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